

The Dark Side Of The Entrepreneur Personality And Small Medium Enterprise Performance Through Mediating Role Of Hubris Behavior: An Empirical Assessment

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Abstract

The main goal is to examine the relationship between entrepreneur narcissism and SMEs performance. Although existing research examines mediating relationships between them in terms of hubristic behavior, we adopt a different approach by examining their differences in relation to the employee and leadership. Using management theories and literature, current research revealed how entrepreneurs' personalities and behavior influence SMEs' performance and act as a strong bridge between them. The study collected data from 255 employees working in various SMEs across Punjab-Pakistan and provided data to their managers/owners. For data analysis, a self-administered questionnaire was used. The outcome is interpreted using a measurement model and regression analysis. Recent findings backed up the theoretical hypothesis.

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Introduction

The significance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in promoting economic growth, generating employment opportunities, reducing poverty, and fostering social cohesion, particularly in developing countries, has been widely acknowledged by scholars (Asad et al., 2018). Consequently, numerous scholars have examined the pivotal role of SMEs in the development of countries. As pointed out by Dar et al. (2017), the success rate of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) remains understated in comparison to their failure rate. According to Oura et al. (2016), the sustained success of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) is contingent upon their ability to maintain a consistent level of innovative activity. However, this can be challenging due to the limited availability of resources within the firm.

According to Hashim (2015), Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) encounter various obstacles that impede their ability to achieve optimal performance. These challenges include deficiencies in skills, resources, knowledge, market access, and strategic planning. Additionally, the personality traits of entrepreneurs may also contribute to these barriers. Undoubtedly, the possession of entrepreneurial competencies can prove advantageous for small enterprises or organisations that are constrained by limited financial resources and the technological infrastructure. According to Peric et al. (2017), the competencies refer to the skills required to effectively utilize resources for enhancing performance of the small and medium enterprises while accomplishing a task. Likewise, the possession of entrepreneurial competencies is essential for the effective management of small and nascent businesses. It has been observed that individuals possessing competencies exhibit proficient execution of demanding tasks. Additionally, entrepreneurs are required to cultivate their competencies in order to attain exceptional firm performance. However, it is unfortunate that these enterprises have not performed satisfactorily due to various factors. Franco and Prata (2019) found that the personality of entrepreneurs can serve as a predictor of diverse business outcomes, indicating that personality has the potential to impact business performance. Caliendo, Goethner, and Weibenberge (2020) assert that the performance and psychological commitment of an entrepreneur are influenced by both the personality traits of the entrepreneur and the characteristics of the business.

Numerous academic studies have focused on examining the characteristics commonly associated with entrepreneurs, or the specific attributes that contribute to their success. Kerr, Kerr, and Xu (2018) have provided evidence that personality may serve as the conduit or modality by which certain investigated phenomena elicit both immediate and enduring impacts on corporate performance. There exists a paucity of research on the impact of the founder's personality and role on the performance of firms, as noted by Lin, Lin, and Fang (2022). The current state of the research on the correlation between the psychological personality traits of top executives,

such as narcissistic personality, and the value of their respective firms is yet to yield conclusive results (Capalbo, Frino, Lim, Mollica, & Palumbo, 2017). According to Yook and Lee (2019), employers who exhibit narcissistic tendencies seek to garner attention, admiration, and praise while evading criticism, ultimately leading to a decline in enterprise performance. The achievement of business success and the longevity of a company are widely recognised as primary objectives for all business stakeholders (Hidayat & Murwartiningsih, 2018).

On the other hand, results identified that one of the issues that affect firms as well as shareholders performance is their high level of confidence and managers need to take reasonable decisions to get high rate of return on investment. According to Ham et al. (2017), a tendency for risk-taking can be influenced by managers who exhibit excessive confidence. According to Duellman et al. (2015), the trait of overconfidence in managers is a crucial aspect that impacts the level of risk-taking in business. These personality traits are quite related to narcissist personality trait that influence on performance of business either large and small medium enterprises. In contrast, narcissism is linked to individuals exhibiting feelings of pride, superiority, and admiration. Another manifestation of narcissism is a severe personality syndrome that is related with excessive self-confidence and has a significant impact on decision-making processes of managers. Most of the managers due to overconfidence makes major mistakes in the process of decision making that negatively influences on firm's performance (Salehi, Naeini & Rouhi, 2020).

Therefore, narcissistic leaders seek to negative impact on firm's performance especially small and medium enterprises because SMEs have lack of resources to handle risky situation and narcissistic behaviors of their leaders. However, empirical research studies in the field of management science have not extensively investigated personality factors as possible indicators of performance. The objective of this research is to fill the gap in the current body of literature by investigating the influence of narcissistic personality characteristics demonstrated by small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) entrepreneurs on their performance in Pakistan. Moreover, not only the narcissistic behaviors are considered as the darker side of leader's personality that impact on firm's performance. There is some potential mechanism that are more influential to consider as that darker impact on enterprises performance. Individuals with narcissistic tendencies leverage their power and authoritative positions to uphold a deeply ingrained, elevated self-image. As a result, they often embody the quintessential leader archetype, which can significantly influence overall performance. Likewise, the negative and egocentric conduct exhibited by leaders is linked to hubristic tendencies. According to Park et al. (2018), the combination of excessive self-assurance, haughtiness, and conceit can be perilous. The aforementioned behaviors are commonly exhibited by individuals in positions of leadership, such as heads of state, executive directors, and managers (Sheaffer & Eckhous, 2017). The aforementioned phenomenon is associated with behavioral disorders, narcissistic personality disorder, and potential addictive behaviours among managers whose connection with reality gradually decreases as their reasoning power is reduced by the power they possess (Pincus and Lukowitsky, 2011).

According to Sadler Smith et al. (2016), empirical evidence suggests that leaders who exhibit hubristic tendencies display an exceptionally high level of self-assurance, overestimate their own capabilities, and tend to disregard the potential for errors. Consequently, such leaders tend to engage in high-risk behaviours in their managerial pursuits. To clarify, hubris results in an inflated sense of confidence in one's own judgements, causing a departure from impartial criteria and a cognitive prejudice that can impact one's decision-making abilities, ultimately resulting in subpar performance. The study conducted by Zhang et al. (2018) has shown that in the field of management, decisions made without the use of decision-making systems and procedures have led to increased costs for companies due to hubristic behaviour. Leaders who possess such a personality type typically prioritise the maintenance of their own image and interests, leading to an increase in narcissistic tendencies and arrogance. This can hinder their ability to acknowledge and accept their limitations (Eckhaus & Sheaffer, 2018).

Consequently, individuals may hold the belief that their decisions are not open to debate or critique, which can have a negative effect on the performance and overall worth of a company. The management science literature frequently engages in a discourse regarding the factors that influence the decision-making process by managers and their consequent impact on organisational performance. In recent years, there has been an increasing scholarly focus on the psychological and behavioural dimensions of leaders and their impact on organisational results. However, there has been a dearth of research on the extreme emotional side and personality characteristics of leaders, particularly those of entrepreneur leadership, and their influence on the performance of small to medium-sized enterprises. The aim of the present investigation is to analyse the intermediary function of hubris conduct exhibited by entrepreneur leaders in the relationship between narcissistic personality trait and the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

The Upper Echelon Theory (UET) was introduced by Hambrick and Mason (1984) and suggests that top-level executives, particularly those who are young owners/leaders and entrepreneurs, base their decision-making on their personal perception of reality. This interpretation is based on the cognitive processes, beliefs, and personality traits of the executives in question. Regarding this matter, it is argued that individuals who exhibit extreme personality traits and hubristic behaviour may initially make decisions that are perceived as appropriate and strategic. However, over time, this approach may lead to a risky decision-making process that ultimately has a negative impact on their performance.

Literature Review

Entrepreneur Narcissistic Personality Trait and SMEs Performance.

The definition of Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) varies across different contexts. SMEs have been defined by various nations based on their anticipated contribution to the country's economy. The categorization of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) has been influenced by various factors, including a nation's level of industrial development and economic indicators, as noted by Iqbal et al. (2017). Musa and Chinniah (2016) have identified that Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are distinguished by their dimensions, which are ascertained by their workforce and the aggregate value of their assets or the extent of their working capital.

Small Enterprises have been defined by the European Union (EU) as commercial entities that employ between 10-250 individuals, generate revenue ranging from \$10 to \$50 million in turnover, and/or possess assets valued between \$10- \$49 Million, as stated by Bubou et al. (2014) and Bello Rogo et al. (2018). As per the findings of Bello Rogo et al. (2018), an organisation can be categorised as a Medium Enterprise (ME) if its total workforce is less than 250 and its turnover rate does not exceed €50 million, or if it maintains a financial balance sheet of at least €43 million. In 2016, the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Authority (SMEDA) furnished a definition for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). As per the definition provided by SMEDA, Medium Enterprises are distinguished by their workforce size of 51-250 employees and a capital cushion of Rs.150 million and an annual sales revenue of up to Rs.800 million. Conversely, Small Enterprises are characterised by a maximum of 50 employees and a yearly revenue of Rs.150 million.

The existing body of literature has identified numerous challenges that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) encounter in the context of developing nations, particularly in Malaysia and China. The text underscores several issues that impede high performance, including deficiencies in leadership capabilities and resource constraints. Several factors have been identified by numerous studies as significant challenges encountered by Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Pakistan. These factors have been found to have a considerable impact on the operations of SMEs in the country (Asad et al., 2018). However, there remains a dearth of literature on the influence of leaders' personal beliefs, personality traits, and behaviour on SMEs in Pakistan.

While some early work has suggested that personality disposition considered as important factor in an entrepreneur performance. Studies examines that firms performance is negatively related to rivalry-based narcissism (Bachrach, Guedes, Harms, & Patel, 2022). Literature also provides importance of owners, chief executives personality and narcissism playing a central role, Cragun et al., (2020) stated that narcissistic traits of leaders effects on organizations' performance. In line with, large organizations and corporate sectors survive but SMEs face numerous issues including firm's performance. Indeed, narcissism considered as one of the most recurrent personality traits and its dark side leads to low empathy, most arrogant, envy from others and negatively influence on performance of leaders as well as organizations ((Braun, 2017). Another study find out that high arrogant leaders take risks in decision making process that might target institutions performance. Lack of firms performance mostly due to high extra confidence of leaders on their own abilities (Rovelli, Massis, & Gomez-Mejia, 2022). Scholars have recently been focusing on the impact of leaders' narcissism on firm performance. Narcissism is characterised by an individual's inflated self-view and a strong desire for continuous reinforcement of that view (Chatterjee & Pollack, 2017).

Thus, we posit that,

Hypothesis1(H1); Entrepreneur narcissism negatively related to SMEs performance in Pakistan.

Hubris Behavior As a Mediator

The origin of the term hubris can be traced back to Greek mythology, where it represents a perilous amalgamation of excessive self-assurance, lofty aspirations, conceit, and haughtiness. The phenomenon of hubris has been observed across various domains such as politics, business, military, scientific research, academia, entertainment, sports, and medicine, among others (Diamandis & Bouras, 2018). Sadler-Smith and Tourish (2021) posit that leaders who display hubris have a tendency to overestimate the likelihood of favourable

outcomes while simultaneously underestimating the likelihood of unfavourable outcomes. This behaviour can result in situations that inadvertently invite adverse consequences. Following this, scholars in the field of management have employed the notion of hubris to showcase the adverse outcomes of an inflated sense of self-assurance. According to Paunonen et al. (2006), empirical evidence suggests that leaders who exhibit hubristic tendencies are prone to causing a decline in their organization's value, breaching ethical standards, adversely affecting employee contentment, and overestimating the potential returns from venturing into novel products and markets. Previous research has demonstrated that hubris behaviour is associated with mental concepts such as overconfidence and narcissism.

According to Pocock (2016), the tendency to overestimate one's own abilities and the anticipated results when evaluating one's skills is not entirely indicative of narcissism. Narcissism is a cognitive personality trait that is distinguished by an inflated sense of self-importance, an intense longing for excessive attention and admiration, challenges in interpersonal relationships, and a lack of ability to empathize with others (Caligor, Levy, & Yeomans, 2015). Indeed, people with hubristic behavior, considered him/herself all in all and give more attention to his/ her decisions that increases that chances of lack of empathy with others or increase the narcissism as well as boost-up overtime. Initial research has indicated that hubris is not merely an attitude, but rather a manifestation of negative behaviour. According to Owen (2012), the diagnosis of hubris syndrome involves the presence of a narcissistic personality trait, which leads individuals to view the world primarily as a platform for exercising power and pursuing glory. Additional indicators encompass an inflated sense of self-assurance in one's own discernment, neglect of counsel and disapproval from others, an undue fixation on appearance and portrayal, and a robust association with the institution or nation to the extent that one's interests are viewed as congruent with those of the collective. Numerous studies have investigated the issue of leadership hubris and have found it to be a significant concern in numerous organisations (Hayward & Hambrick, 1997).

Leaders who have hubristic behavior mostly prefer to impose their own decisions on others and sometimes their overconfidence on themselves develop narcissistic personality and badly impact on firms performance (Berger et al., 2020). Furthermore, extant literature has established that the confidence of entrepreneurial leaders, which is socially constructed, influences their interpretation of information pertaining to their ventures. This, in turn, has implications for the positive and negative outcomes that ensue. According to literature, it has been suggested that entrepreneurs have a tendency to underestimate their abilities (Mueller and Shepherd, 2016). In addition to the Hubris theory of entrepreneurship, there are other theoretical frameworks that have been proposed to explain the behaviour and decision-making of entrepreneurs. HTE (Hayward et al., 2006) is an extremely significant theory explaining the reason certain businessmen are especially susceptible to starting up fresh businesses under a high probability of business failure. The concept of confidence as a socially constructed phenomenon is a central focus of HTE, as posited by Bollaert and Petit (2010). According to this perspective, entrepreneurs' beliefs regarding the success of their projects are not solely based on objective assessments of their expertise, expertise, and the project's qualities. Rather, their high level for trust in their abilities to navigate risky situations and their tendency towards overconfidence can contribute to the failure of their ventures, as noted by Poblete (2022). The phenomenon of HTE sheds light on the negative impact of excessive self-assurance over time, which not only dissuades entrepreneurs from initiating business ventures but also impedes their pursuit of ambitious growth strategies, particularly in adverse circumstances where resources are limited. The core element of HET determined that individuals think about themselves or having narcissistic personality trait most leads to negative outcomes like lack of enterprises performance. From the all above and existing theories support that entrepreneur hubristic behaviors' cause of some psychological factors and personality traits including narcissism that negative impact on firms performance. That means hubristic behavior as a interlink mechanism between entrepreneur personality and their impact on firms performance. Hence , we hypothesized as;

H2: Hubristic behavior mediates in the relationship between entrepreneur narcissistic personality and SMEs performance.

Theoretical Framework

Hubristic Behavior of
Entrepreneur

Figure 1 . Theoretical Framework

Methodology

This study relied on pilot tests to determine the reliability and validity of the instruments. The goal of this pilot study was to assess the opinions of Medium Enterprise owners/managers (Salman et al., 2016a). As a result, the total of 80 questionnaires were distributed at random via email and personal visit. The pilot study's sample size was relatively limited. The present investigation employed a self-administered questionnaire as the primary data collection instrument. Sekaran and Bougie (2016) posit that the utilisation of self-distributed questionnaires can foster comprehension with survey participants and enhance the rate of response. In addition, the variables that are of interest were rated using five-point Likert scales. Of the total 80 questionnaires disseminated, 58 were retrieved, albeit 7 of them were inaccurately filled out.

Consequently, a total of 51 questionnaires were utilised for the purpose of evaluating the reliability and validity of the instruments. However, due to distribution and personal delivery, the response rate was approximately 85%. The present study is concerned with establishing the reliability and validity of the instruments employed, in order to ensure that they accurately measure the intended concept (Hair, 2007; Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Similar to other studies, this one also tested reliability, but it did so using Cronbach's alpha, which is the most popular method (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). The present investigation employed the SPSS 23.0 Mac edition to verify the precision of the measurements utilised in the final analysis. The present study employed a time-lag research design and utilised a quantitative approach by administering a questionnaire to assess the impact of narcissistic personality traits in entrepreneurs on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), as well as the manifestation of hubris behavior in the context of Pakistan. The study focused on Small and Medium Enterprise Development (SMEDA) and gathered data from employees employed in various SMEs located throughout Pakistan.

Sample size

Non-random, convenient sampling techniques were taken into consideration when determining the sample size. In the first time lag, the data actually the part of the study was 255. In the second time lag, we again distribute data to the same respondents and get results after a gap of three weeks. We distributed 400 questionnaires, but only received 288 responses, and out of these, few questionnaires were not completely filled out. The information was gathered from various cities in Punjab, Pakistan, between September and November of 2022.

Procedure to collect the Data.

This study focuses on the manufacturing industry and uses Pakistani industrial SMEs as its population and universe. Because it meets the criteria chosen for this empirical study, the manufacturing/Textile industry sector is taken into consideration for the purposes of this research.

Since a questionnaire is a tool that can convey a lot of information, it was used to conduct this study's data collection, investigating the impact of the founder's unique qualities and personality traits on the success of SMEs and the hubristic actions of leaders. We concentrated on gathering information from the working employees about the nature, traits, behavior, and impact of their owners on the performance of their firms in order to eliminate the errors in empirical study. To begin with, the unit of analysis was the individual employee, who was treated as a part of the study rather than dyadic data. After that, data was collected using self-administrative adopted questionnaires. All of the instruments use the same Likert scale, which has a 5-point scale with a range of 1-strongly disagree to 5-strongly agree.

Additionally, we evaluated narcissistic leaders using the NPI-16 item scale (Ames et al., 2006). In addition to the questionnaire on enterprise performance that Morgan & Strong adopted in 2003 with five item scales,

another questionnaire based on the hypothesised symptoms of hubris syndrome as described by Owen & Davidson (2006) was also administered. For this study, we chose the three variables of interest because they were all required to have reliability and internal consistency with a Cronbach's alpha value above .6. In order to assess the impact of the founder's unique qualities and personality traits on the performance of SMEs, four demographic variables were also taken into account: age, gender, tenure, and year of firm foundation.

Sample Characteristics

The demographics of this study include the age, gender, tenure, and year of firm foundation. The demographic characteristics of the population under investigation may exert an influence on the study, potentially affecting the variables and their interrelationships. Only one type of questionnaire was distributed and to be filled by employees who are the part of SMEs. The sample size of current study was 255 working employees in SMEs-Pakistan. To check the influences of these variables, checked the characteristics of these demographic and their ratio. The details of samples characteristics are detailed below in given table:

TABLE1: Demographic variables

Sr#	SMEs employees	Valid	Frequency (N 255)	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	Age	20-30	144	56.5	56.5
		31-40	75	29.4	85.9
		41-50	36	14.1	100.0
2	Gender	Male	198	77.6	77.6
		Female	57	22.4	100.0
3	Tenure	0-5	132	51.8	51.8
		6-10	59	23.1	74.9
		10-15	64	25.1	100.0
4	Year of Firm	1 year	77	30.2	30.2
		2-5 years	73	28.6	58.8
		6-10 years	43	16.9	75.7
		10 above	62	24.3	100.0

The above table depicted that Age, Gender, Tenure as well as Year of Firm are important demographic variables which are used to measure the purpose of the respondent as well as researchers that identify that research belong to the above group. Table 3 illustrates that 56.5% of the respondents fall within the age range of 20 to 30, indicating a significant proportion of the sample. Individuals with the age of 31 to 40 belongs respondent that is 29.4 and people with in the age of 41 to 50 belong to the group with 14.1 percent. Similarly, like age, Gender also considered as an important factor that 77.6 percent are male respondent and 22.4 percent female respondent. The research included tenure as a demographic variable, as it serves as an indicator of an individual's level of expertise. This aids in enhancing comprehension of the variables pertaining to the distinctions between long-serving employees and newly hired employees. The above table shows the percentages. As the table shows that 51.3 percent employees have 0-5yr tenured in the enterprise and 23.1 percent have 6- 10 yr tenured whereas, only 25.1 percent have 10-15 yr tenured. Moreover, current study also checked the position or year of firm. It means that how much year enterprise have to run business activities. The above result showed that 30.2 percent firms have only year and 28.6 percent have 2-5 years, 16.9 percent have 6-10 years and 24.3 percent have consumed above 10 years in business.

Control Variables

Control variables such as age, gender, tenure, and the year of the firm were taken into account due to their potential influence on both entrepreneurial narcissistic personality and firm performance. To achieve this objective, a one-way ANOVA test was conducted to determine the statistical significance of the variables.

TABLE2: Control Variables

Sr#	Variables	Entrepreneur Narcissistic Personality		Firm's performance	
		<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
1	Age	3.522	0.594	3.244	0.963

2	Gender	2.403	0.526	2.295	0.588
3	Tenure	3.626	0.536	1.463	0.046
4	Year of Firm	1.069	0.043	.	0.021

Based on the ANOVA test results, it can be concluded that, with the exception of tenure and year of firm, the variables examined in this study have no significant impact on firms' performance. Therefore, it is necessary to control only the tenure and year of firms when evaluating firm performance, as the p-value is greater than 0.05. The results presented in Table 3.2 indicate that age does not have a significant impact on entrepreneurial narcissistic personality ($p = 0.594$) or firm performance ($p = 0.963$). Likewise, the statistical significance of gender is negligible, as evidenced by the respective p-values of 0.526 for ENP and 0.588 for FP. Tenure however, has a insignificant impact on ($p=0.536$) for entrepreneurial narcissistic personality but has a significant value for firms performance ($p=.046$) need to be controlled. Year of firm is significant for both variables ($p=0.043$, $p=0.021$) hence, need to be controlled.

Reliability Analysis of the Scale

Reliability analysis is the method in which the item or scale is tested several times and consistently produces the same results. The scale's reliability means that it can produce consistent results over and over again when tested many times. The research utilises Cronbach's alpha coefficient as a metric to assess the reliability of the data. This demonstrates the intra-consistency of a unidimensional construct and variable, as well as the correlation between these variables. The Cronbach alpha coefficient is constrained to the range of 0 to 1. The higher value corresponds to higher reliability, while the smaller value corresponds to lower reliability. In this study, Cronbach's alpha values above 0.7 are taken into account when measuring a chosen set of constructs, while values below 0.7 are taken into account as less reliable.

Table 3: Values of Cronbach's Alpha

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Items
Entrepreneur Narcissistic Personality	0.945	16
Hubristic Behavior	0.908	14
Firms Performance	0.911	05

Measurement Model

To examine the measurement model, the CFA (Confirmatory factor analysis) method is used. The model consists of three latent variables: entrepreneur narcissistic personality, hubristic behavior, and SMEs performance. The model fit was evaluated using a combination of fit indices such as RMSEA, TLI, CFI, chi-square model, and IFI. Table 2 shows that the measurement model produced promising results with IFI = 0.926, TLI = 0.906, CFI = 0.88, and RMSEA = 0.032. The three -factor model's CFA results were consistent. The variable factor loading values show that they were perfectly loaded. Strauss et al., (2000) established 0.05 as the ideal criterion for testing RMSEA, with a value less than 0.05 considered the best fit and the value of RAMSEA as 0.032 is accurate

TABLE4: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Model	Factor	X2	df	RMSEA	IFI	TLI	CFI
	Three Factors	522.829	431	.043	.899	.869	.887

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is a statistical technique employed to establish the association between distinct variables. The purpose of the correlation analysis in this study is to investigate the correlation between an entrepreneurial narcissistic personality and firm performance. The study specifically concentrates on the mediating effect of hubristic behaviour demonstrated by the entrepreneur. The variable "Entrepreneur" exhibits a sample mean of 4.16 and a corresponding standard deviation of 0.67. The sample's mean score for hubristic behaviour is 4.01, with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.67. The performance of the firms is represented by a statistical measure of central tendency, specifically the mean, which has a value of 2.99. Additionally, the variability of the firms' performance is measured by the standard deviation, which has a value of 0.84.

Table 5: Means, Standard Deviation, Correlation

S.No.	Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3
1	Entrepreneur narcissistic personality	4.16	0.67	1		
2	Hubristic Behavior	4.01	0.67	0.462**	1	
3	Firms Performance	2.99	0.84	-0.404**	-0.39**	1

***Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). N=255*

The correlation table 5 indicates a statistically significant positive relationship between the variables. Analyzing the values one by one, we can see that entrepreneurial personality and hubristic behavior has a value of $r = 0.462^{**}$, at $p < 0.01$. ENP has significant but negative correlation with firms performance $r = -0.404^{**}$. Similarly, hubristic behavior is negatively but significantly correlated with firms performance, the value showed that $r = -0.39^{**}$, $p < 0.01$.

Regression Analysis

Correlational analysis indicates the existence of an association between variables; however, it does not establish the causative nature of the relationship. The study employed correlation analysis to validate the presence of a connection among the variables. Nonetheless, this level of information is inadequate for the intended research objectives, thus necessitating the utilisation of regression analysis. Regression analysis is a statistical technique utilised to ascertain the extent of correlation between two variables. This validates the interdependence of variables. Hayes & Preacher (2013) used the regression analysis method for moderating and mediating variables. The impact of psychological well-being as a moderator was investigated using mediation analysis. Model 1 of Hayes & Preacher (2014) is used to test the moderating effect of ILC.

TABLE 6: Mediation Analysis

Sr#	Variables	β	SE	P-value
1	ENPFP	-.489	.070	.000
2	ENPHB $\longrightarrow$	-.567	.075	.003
3	ENPHBFP $\longrightarrow$	-.596	.083	.008

Note: Bootstrap sample size 5000. LL = lower limit; CI = confidence interval; UL = upper limit; ENP= entrepreneur narcissistic personality, HB= Hubristic behavior, FP= firm's performance.

Interpretation: The table above depicts the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Beta and P-values revealed appositive significance between them, as well as a HB between entrepreneur narcissistic personality and SMEs performance. . Hypotheses 1 and 2 are thus accepted.

Discussion

The present research investigated the influence of entrepreneurial narcissism on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and their self-important conduct in the region of Punjab, Pakistan. The performance of small and medium enterprises plays a significant role in the process of industrialization and is closely linked to the personality traits and behavioural patterns exhibited by the entrepreneur. The results showed that narcissistic business owners had a negative impact on the success of their organization. This particular result was consistent with earlier research by Wiklund & Shepherd (2011), who showed that entrepreneurs with

narcissistic personality traits have a stronger influence on weaker firms' performance. The narcissism of owners can have a separate impact on firm strategy-making and performance variance, as shown by (Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2007). The current study adds to earlier research by Resick et al. (2009) on the detrimental effects of narcissism as a leadership trait. This belief that narcissism is a dark leadership trait and is detrimental to a company's performance is generally supported by later analyses (Wales, Patel & Lumpkin, 2013). Another significant finding of this study is the negative impact of narcissism, a dark personality trait of leaders, on firms' performance (Petrenko et al., 2016).

Furthermore, research has indicated that an individual's inclination towards risk-taking has a positive effect on their entrepreneurial abilities, albeit lacking statistical significance. Stated differently, the importance of developing competency outweighed the willingness to take risks. In addition, the proclivity to engage in risky behaviour exhibited a deleterious albeit statistically insignificant effect on business performance. The findings indicate that an inclination towards risk-taking may have an adverse effect on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). According to Smith et al. (2018), the personality of individuals within an organisation can have a cascading effect, permeating throughout the business and ultimately impacting its outcomes. The scholarly discourse pertaining to social exchange theory (SET) elucidates the conduct of individuals in social associations in a comparable manner. The literature posits that entrepreneurs exhibit a tendency to reciprocate positive and negative treatment when perceiving social relationships as a sequence of transactions and obligations. Based on recent statistical data, it has been observed that leaders who exhibit self-centered thinking, prioritise their own decisions, and respond unfavourably (such as through aggressive behaviour) towards their subordinates, tend to have a detrimental effect on the performance of both the individuals and the organisation as a whole (Grijalva et al., 2019).

From this foundation, we also developed a theory about the crucial role of hubristic behaviour as a significant mediator by which the performance of SMEs is impacted by narcissistic entrepreneur leadership. Therefore, our model encompasses not only how personality traits affect performance but also some interlinking mechanisms that help to establish a connection between them. For instance, hubristic behavior such as excessive arrogance, excessive pride, and a refusal to heed advice cause powerful people in positions of authority to overstep their bounds, with detrimental effects on both themselves and others (Diamandis & Bouras, 2018). According to management researchers, "exaggerated self-confidence" has detrimental effects, which are illustrated by the hubris concept (Malmendier & Taylor, 2015). A later study looked at how hubristic leaders were more likely to violate integrity standards, diminish the value of their company, and harm their reputation (Blickle, Schlegel, Fassbender, & Klein, 2006).

Practical Implication of the Study.

The prevalence of hubris and/or narcissism among leaders is a notable phenomenon in both contemporary politics and corporate governance. Consequently, it is imperative for managers, executive teams, and board members to comprehend the manner in which influential positions facilitate the emergence of narcissistic and hubristic leaders, and the ways in which such leaders employ and exploit their positions. The aim of this study was to investigate the influence of narcissistic personality characteristics among entrepreneurs on the operational outcomes of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) located in Pakistan. The objective of this study is to investigate the intermediary function of hubristic conduct in the context of entrepreneurial leadership.

Theoretically, this study contributed to Upper Echelon Theory (UET) by investigating the effect of entrepreneurial personality characteristics on leader behaviour and enterprise performance, particularly the indirect effect of hubristic behaviour, in order to uncover the complex relationship between them. This study highlights the managerial implications of dark side entrepreneurial leaders and their impact on enterprise performance. It advocates for the promotion of entrepreneurial activity in new firms and small to medium-sized enterprises while minimising any negative effects. Given that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) contribute to 30% of Pakistan's gross domestic product (GDP), it is imperative to examine the leadership characteristics that are essential for ensuring the continued success and viability of these ventures. These traits play a crucial role in shaping the overall reputation and performance of SMEs.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Pakistan encounter various limitations as a result of the unstable economic conditions. The implementation of conflicting policies has impeded the advancement of these sectors. Small enterprises within the state operate as autonomous entities with minimal regulatory oversight, resulting in challenges in obtaining financial services and funding as required. Thus, acquiring a narcissistic personality in SMEs leadership destroys the firm's value. It is the civic duty of management science researchers to develop such plans and strategies for SMEs leadership, as well as training programmes to encourage entrepreneur leaders.

Furthermore, working in such small businesses and appreciating their abilities to avoid overconfidence and hubristic behaviour that wrecks havoc on the performance of SMEs.

Conclusion

People's psychological characteristics like narcissism influence their decisions. As a result, one aspect of narcissism has a detrimental impact on people's judgement. As a result, it alters or enhances their performance. When challenged, entrepreneurs with these characteristics are viewed as having false self-confidence, little social empathy, and hostility (Blinkhorn et al., 2016; Guedes, 2017; Nevicka et al., 2011). There are unfortunately many obstacles that SMEs must overcome in order to grow and contribute to the GDP of any nation. There has been a great deal of prior research in the field of business studies on the role that challenges and risk-oriented factors play in the value and performance of businesses. As a result, this study pinpointed some of the most crucial aspects of how an entrepreneur's personality affects the success of their ventures, and last but not least, how narcissistic entrepreneurs' hubristic behaviors may act as a mediating factor between them in Pakistan. Since high levels of narcissism among leaders, managers, or shareholders may have an impact on a company's performance, SMEs should consider these factors as well as how to calm down their hubristic behaviour when making decisions in order to control the risk-taking of their businesses.

Limitations and Future Directions

This study revealed the negative personality traits of entrepreneur leaders and their impact on the performance of SMEs. In this context, some statistical tests have been performed to support the current hypothesis, but there are still a few gaps that may be filled in the future by us or other potential researchers. Future research can look into the effects of an entrepreneur's narcissistic personality on employee turnover intentions and performance, as well as the comparison of the dark and bright sides of a highly confident entrepreneur and their consequences in major financial and non-financial firm decisions.

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